

GREEN AIRPORT, THE NEW ERA OF SUSTAINABILITY

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Abstract

Going Green is an important ingredient of new age processing. It has different aspects like Green computing, Green processing, Green building, Green development, Green Healthcare and many. This research is about Green technology trends in airline industry and concentrates on airport infrastructure. When a huge infrastructure is built it has impact on nearby environment. One cannot imagine in how many ways it impact on ecosystem. Green Building is the way things have to be done in future. Green building uses resources optimally, produces less waste and provides desired output having long term benefits for mankind. The analysis is conducted on Solar Power generation capabilities and consumption of generated Power of Cochin Airport Authority. This Analysis reveals the best practices that Airport around India can adopt with slight increase in use of available resources. This implementation will definitely help in Business Sustainability and less CO2 emission under large Infrastructural Projects.

Key words: Green Computing, Business Sustainability, Green Building, CO2 emission.

Introduction

Green Building or Green Construction is structural process, responsible for environmental friendliness and Resource efficiency. It covers entire building infrastructure from Designing, Construction, Operation, Maintenance, Renovation and Deconstruction. Going green majorly deals with using natural resources for generation of power and emitting lesser hazardous material out. Recent trends have seen developments, where PPPs are getting encouragement from government policies for infrastructures such as Railway Stations, Sports Complex, Multiplex, Mall, Highway and Airports. This requires lots of natural resources such as water, sand, metals etc. In a world exhausting our natural resources, green building has become the ethical “in-thing” in an attempt to save our planet from despair. This, however, can only be achieved through a concerted effort by architects, engineers and construction companies – and of course, the support of the concerned citizen. As per India's Directorate General of Civil Aviation (DGCA) there are 101 domestic airports with overall operational Airports have been increased by 10 since last 5 years (as per last data updated on DGCA website on 16th October 2018). Hence this study was concentrated on Airport Infrastructures and Green Building.

Cochin Airport

Source: www.CIAL.aero

CIAL is fifth Airport constructed on PPP Model in India. State Government of Kerala is largest stakeholder and there is no foreign Stakeholder involved. CIAL is the biggest international Airport in Kerala. It is the fourth busiest airport in terms of international passenger volumes and the seventh busiest in terms of total passenger volumes. It is also one of the most profitable airports in the country. Commissioned in 1999, CIAL started making profits from 2003-04, its fourth year of operation. In financial year 2014- 2015, CIAL reported a profit after tax of `144.58 Cr, with a gross income of `414 Cr, an increase of 14.4% from the previous year. Years of uncertainties and struggles starting right from conceptual stages and all through its formative stages have shaped a unique character for CIAL, the strength of which is driving it from success to glory, taking occasional setbacks in its stride.

Particular	Description
Name	Cochin International Airport Limited (CIAL)
Inauguration of Green Building	18 th August 2015
Total Cost	Rs 65 Cr
Solar Panels laid	46,150
Area Covered by Solar panels	18 hectares
Power requirement per day	48000 Units
Actual Power Production per day	50000 Units
CO2 emission avoided	300000 tonnes over 25 years
Photovoltaic Module	265 Wp
Inverters	1 MW (no battery storage)

Source: http://cial.aero/userfiles/CIAL_SCMS.pdf

Performance

I.Performance Analysis: The section begins with the performance analysis of the 12 MWP from measured solar irradiation data and energy generation data. The predicated plant performance by PV system and Solar GIS software are discussed and compared with measured values. Also the economic and environment aspects of utility scale power plant are presented in detail. The power output from the plant varies with the solar insolation and ambient temperature. The monthly averaged daily solar irradiation is maximum during March (5.66Kwh/m²) and is minimum in the month of July (3.39Kwh/m²). Similarly the ambient temperature value of 29.67oC in the monsoon month July and reaches a peak value of 35.5oC in March from the values. It can be inferred that the value of solar irradiation and temperature depends seasonal variation. The wind speed available in

this region is low (less than 3m/s) and it influence in power o/p is negligible from the monitored one year data (sept-2015 to Aug 2016). The monthly energy generation reached peak value in March during that month (206Kwh/m²). The energy output was found to be least in the month of June and July due to rainy and humid climate. The electrical energy was sold to Kerala State Electricity Board (KSEB) at fixed rate through net metering system.

II.Control: The 12MWp solar plant is receiving maximum global irradiation in the month of march(197KWH/m²) and lowest in the month of June(122KWH/m²). The similar variation can be seen in the diffused radiation values as well. The shading losses are negligibly small as the plant is located in vast shade free land. The maximum monthly energy yield(ESM) can be observed in march(151KWh/KWp) while it touches minimum value in June and July. SolarGIS predicts a cumulative annual energy generation (ETM) of 17630MWh(17.63GWh). The performance ratio varies from 74.4% to 77.5%throughout the year and its annual average value is 76%.

III.Performance comparison: The SCADA performance data system is compared with those simulated using PVSyst and SolarGIS software. The slight difference in the energy generation values can be attributed to the variation in measured and predicted meteorological parameters.

IV.Helping in Revenue: The conception, birth and growth of CIAL in the most difficult and unsympathetic environment brought in parsimony in spending in its operation philosophy. They know that saving money is easier than making it. Though CIAL had outsourced majority of its operations it still had to pay the power bill to KSEB, the state owned power utility, for all its power consuming operations in the Airport at a commercial tariff rate of Rs 8.30 per unit. The facilities in CIAL required about 48000 units of power every day which meant a clean draining of about Rs 4 lac per day from its kitty. This was just unacceptable to CIAL and there was an urge to bring it down. They undertook power saving measures and energy auditing which derived some benefit. However it was evident that generating own power at a cheaper rate was going to be the only lasting solution. There were, however, technological and legal impediments.

Fig: Revenue Generation of CIAL after Green Building

Feasibility:

Since unutilized airport area is used land cost can be saved from capital investment required is around 69.28. Rate at which electricity is sold to grid is 7.00INR per unit the pay back period of this MW scale project is around 5.6 yrs. The project is showing positive NPV(42.55cr) at 10% discount factor. The internal rank of return INR is 17.5%. This show that such projects are economy environment benefit of solar powered airport corresponding to reduction is carbon footprint

Conclusion:

The paper studied effectiveness of fully solar powered airport. In this aspect, the 12 MWP grid connected PV system located at Cochin Airport was monitored annually and its performance was evaluated on monthly average daily basis. The prominent conclusions drawn are

- Buffer zones maintained around airports are ideally suitable for utility scale PV power point.
- From the onsite data, the plant generated 17611.33MWh of electricity during the monitoring period.
- The energy generation values from from PVSyst and SolarGIS are 18889 and 17630MWh respectively.
- The overall functioning of plant is satisfactory with a performance Ratio(PR) of 86.58% and capacity utilization factor of 20.12%.
- It is observed that the plant output is less dependent on ambient temperature.
- The plant performance results using solar simulation software's (PVSyst and SolarGIS) found to match closely with actual site data it is also be concluded that PV design and simulation software such as PVSyst and SolarGIS are capable of predicting the solar plant performance accurately.
- Though the initial investment is high the Net Present Value of project is positive. A slight reduction in investment is possible in the case of airport due to availability of land.
- Cochin airport provides a best practice that can be adopted in airports around the world.

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